

THE SQUARE OF THE FERMAT QUOTIENT

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1. Introduction

Fermat quotients, numbers of the form $(a^{p-1} - 1)/p$, played an important rôle in the study of cyclotomic fields and Fermat's Last Theorem [2]. They seem to appear in many surprising identities, one of the most delightful of which is Glaisher's observation that

$$(1) \quad \frac{2^{p-1} - 1}{p} \equiv -\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{2^1}{1} + \frac{2^2}{2} + \dots + \frac{2^{p-1}}{(p-1)} \right) \pmod{p}.$$

Recently Skula conjectured that

$$(2) \quad \left(\frac{2^{p-1} - 1}{p} \right)^2 \equiv - \left(\frac{2^1}{1^2} + \frac{2^2}{2^2} + \dots + \frac{2^{p-1}}{(p-1)^2} \right) \pmod{p}.$$

It is stunning that such a simple but elegant generalization of (1) should have remained unnoticed for so long. In this note we prove (2), and indeed a further generalization.

One might hazard a guess that the ratio

$$(3) \quad \left(\frac{2^{p-1} - 1}{p} \right)^k \bigg/ \left(\frac{2^1}{1^k} + \frac{2^2}{2^k} + \dots + \frac{2^{p-1}}{(p-1)^k} \right) \pmod{p}$$

should also be a simple fixed rational number for other values of k , but calculations reveal that this is probably not the case.

We will present two proofs of (2), one a substantial simplification of our original proof due to the anonymous referee, the other a different simplification, but both of which contain formulas that are perhaps of independent interest.

2. The main results

Let p be a fixed prime > 3 . Define

$$q(x) = \frac{x^p - (x-1)^p - 1}{p}, \text{ with } g(x) = \sum_{i=1}^{p-1} \frac{x^i}{i} \text{ and } G(x) = \sum_{i=1}^{p-1} \frac{x^i}{i^2}.$$

(Here, and throughout, x is a variable, and the results below are proved for polynomials in x ; of course one may substitute in integers for x to obtain integer congruences.) Standard arguments give that $G(1) \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$. Since $1/r + 1/(p-r) = p/r(p-r)$ thus $2g(1) \equiv -pG(1) \equiv 0 \pmod{p^2}$. Also $G(-1) = \sum_{1 \leq j \leq (p-1)/2} (1/(2j)^2 - 1/(p-2j)^2) \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$.

We will prove the functional equation

$$(4) \quad G(x) \equiv G(1-x) + x^p G(1-1/x) \pmod{p},$$

as well as the two “mod p -identities”

$$(5) \quad q(x)^2 \equiv -2x^p G(x) - 2(1-x^p)G(1-x) \pmod{p}$$

and

$$(6) \quad -G(x) \equiv \frac{1}{p}(q(x) + g(1-x)) \pmod{p}$$

which lead to two different proofs of (2): Substituting $x = 2$ into (5) and then into (6) we obtain

$$q(2)^2 \equiv -2^{p+1}G(2) - 2(1-2^p)G(-1) \equiv -4G(2) \pmod{p}$$

which is (2), and then

$$-G(2) \equiv \frac{1}{p}(q(2) + g(-1)) \pmod{p}$$

which gives (2) from Glaisher’s result [1] that $g(-1) \equiv -q(2) + pq(2)^2/4 \pmod{p^2}$.

3. Proofs

We begin with the trivial observation that $\binom{p-1}{j}(-1)^j \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$ for all $0 \leq j \leq p-1$. Then

$$q'(x) = x^{p-1} - (x-1)^{p-1} = -\sum_{j=0}^{p-2} \binom{p-1}{j} (-x)^j \equiv -\sum_{i=1}^{p-1} x^{i-1} = -g'(x) \pmod{p}.$$

This, together with the fact that $q(x)$ and $g(x)$ both have degree $< p$, implies that $q(x) + g(x) \equiv c_0 \pmod{p}$ for some constant c_0 . Substituting in $x = 0$ we discover that $c_0 \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$ and so

$$(7) \quad q(x) + g(x) \equiv 0 \pmod{p}.$$

It is immediate from their definitions that $q(x) = q(1 - x)$ and $g(x) \equiv -x^p g(1/x) \pmod{p}$. From these observations and (7) we deduce that $g(x) \equiv -q(x) = -q(1 - x) \equiv g(1 - x) \pmod{p}$ and $x^p g(1 - 1/x) \equiv x^p g(1/x) \equiv -g(x) \pmod{p}$. Now $G'(x) = g(x)/x$ and so

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dx}(G(1 - x) + x^p G(1 - 1/x)) &\equiv -\frac{g(1 - x)}{(1 - x)} + x^p \frac{g(1 - 1/x)}{x^2(1 - 1/x)} \\ &= \frac{xg(1 - x) + x^p g(1 - 1/x)}{x(x - 1)} \equiv \frac{g(x)}{x} = G'(x) \pmod{p}, \end{aligned}$$

and therefore $G(x) - G(1 - x) - x^p G(1 - 1/x) \equiv c_1 \pmod{p}$ for some constant c_1 . Substituting in $x = 1$ we discover that $c_1 \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$ and so (4) holds.

Similarly, from the above, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dx}q(x)^2 = 2q(x)q'(x) &\equiv -2g(x) \left(x^{p-1} - \sum_{j=0}^{p-1} x^j \right) \equiv -2x^p \frac{g(x)}{x} + 2(1 - x^p) \frac{g(1 - x)}{(1 - x)} \\ &\equiv -2x^p G'(x) - 2(1 - x^p) G'(1 - x) \\ &\equiv \frac{d}{dx}(-2x^p G(x) - 2(1 - x^p) G(1 - x)) \pmod{p}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $q(x)^2 + 2x^p G(x) + 2(1 - x^p) G(1 - x) \equiv c_2 + c_3 x^p \pmod{p}$ since this polynomial has degree $< 2p$. Substituting in $x = 0$ and $x = 1$ we discover that $c_2 \equiv c_3 \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$ and we have proved (5).

Finally note that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{r=1}^{p-1} \frac{(1 - x)^r - 1}{r} &= \sum_{j=1}^{p-1} \left(\sum_{r=1}^{p-1} \binom{r-1}{j-1} \right) \frac{(-x)^j}{j} = \sum_{j=1}^{p-1} \binom{p-1}{j} \frac{(-x)^j}{j} \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^{p-1} \left(\binom{p}{j} - \binom{p-1}{j-1} \right) \frac{(-x)^j}{j} \\ &= p \sum_{j=1}^{p-1} \left\{ (-1)^j \binom{p-1}{j-1} \right\} \frac{x^j}{j^2} + \frac{(x-1)^p - x^p + 1}{p}, \end{aligned}$$

which implies (6), since each $(-1)^{j-1} \binom{p-1}{j-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$ and as $g(1) \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$.

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